

Cognitive Emotion Regulation and Ability to Delay Gratification among Alcoholic and Non-alcoholic People

Sachin Kumar & Kumkum Pareek
Department of Psychology, R.G. (P.G.) College, Meerut

ABSTRACT

We know that individual with any type of addiction have to go through a series of negative emotions along with the ways of regulating them, in the course of getting addicted. This paper is to investigate the differences between alcoholic and non-alcoholic individuals in terms of use of various cognitive emotion regulation strategies and the ability to delay gratification. This study was conducted in district Saharanpur. Data was collected by using inventories- CERQ of Garnefski and, test for Ability to Delay Gratification on a sample of 104 individuals (alcoholics-42 and non-alcoholics 62), with purposive sampling technique. In order to test the difference between alcoholic and non-alcoholics in terms of predictor variables: ability to delay gratification and various cognitive emotion regulation strategies Discriminant Analysis was employed. Result of the study revealed that ability to delay gratification is positively associated whereas three strategies of cognitive emotion regulation (self-blame, rumination and catastrophizing) are negatively associated with the discrimination function between alcoholic and non-alcoholic people. It means that alcoholic group differed from non-alcoholic group because of having low score on ability to delay gratification and high scores on self-blame, rumination and catastrophizing.

Keywords: Cognitive Emotion Regulation, Ability to Delay Gratification, alcoholic-non-alcoholic.